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Unveiling The Scientific Principles Of Indian Astrology Through Muthuswamy Dikshitar's Navagraha Kritis – With Special Reference To ‘Suryamurthe’ Kriti

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Abstract

Indian astrology, rooted in ancient texts like the Vedas, often faces scepticism from the scientific community. However, Muthuswamy Dikshitar, a prominent Carnatic composer, demonstrated profound knowledge in his Navagraha kritis, which reflect the enduring relationship between astrology and music. Hindu Astrology posits that the nine planets shape human evolution, with their movements through the zodiac marking mankind's progress. This paper critically analyses Dikshitar's composition to reveal the scientific principles underlying Indian Astrology, shedding light on its integration with modern understanding while showcasing the depth of wisdom preserved in music. The harmonious coexistence of astrology and astronomy in Dikshitar's compositions provides a unique bridge between tradition and modernity, fostering a holistic approach to understanding the cosmos and its impact on human existence. In essence, the analysis of Dikshitar's Navagraha kritis not only emphasizes the intricate relationship between astrology and music but also serves as a compelling case for the integration of traditional wisdom with contemporary scientific understanding. It opens avenues for interdisciplinary exploration, encouraging scholars to delve deeper into the intersections of music, astrology, and astronomy to unravel the hidden gems of knowledge that have been preserved through the ages.

Keywords: Indian Astrology, Carnatic music, Muthuswamy Dikshitar, Astronomy

INTRODUCTION

Indian Astrology

Indian astrology, often called Vedic astrology or Jyotish, is a traditional divination method used in India for countless years. Its roots can be traced to the Vedas, the ancient Indian texts. Over time, it has developed into a comprehensive system of astrology that includes many different branches and methods. The positions of the sun, moon, and planets at the moment of birth are all taken into consideration in Indian astrology. An in-depth and nuanced insight into a person's personality, qualities, strengths, weaknesses, and possible life experiences is offered by this holistic approach. Indian astrology analyses and interprets the cosmic effects on an individual's life using a system of 12 houses, 9 planets (including the sun and moon), and different nakshatras (lunar mansions).

Astronomy Vs Astrology

Though in essentially different ways, astronomy and astrology are two separate but related disciplines that deal with celestial objects and their impact on human existence. According to western definition, Astronomy is a scientific discipline that focuses on the study of celestial objects such as stars, planets, galaxies, and cosmic phenomena. Empirical data, careful scientific approach, observation, and experimentation form the foundation of astronomy. Whereas, Astrology is a belief system or metaphysical practice that asserts a relationship between Earthly events and features, especially human lives, and the positions and movements of celestial bodies. Astrology is often regarded as a pseudoscience or a type of divination with no empirical basis, whereas astronomy is based on scientific principles and aims for objectivity and verifiable proof.

Astrology as Science?

Astrology has advanced Science as its base of understanding and Many critics deny that, as there are very limited discoveries are brought out and there are much more to discover in space science relating to astrology. In a study of jyotish which adapted the inclusion, exclusion and substitution of planets, proved that electromagnetism had a major influence on the genesis of the cell at the same time on the origin of human DNA and its coding. (Subba Rao, "Jyotish

Unravels Mystery of Origin of Life”). The majority of the seven octillion atoms that make up an adult human are hydrogen, which was created by the Big Bang approximately 14 billion years ago and is the most prevalent element in the universe. The Sun, the central point of the solar system, is made up of 25% helium and 75% hydrogen. Hydrogen makes up the core strands of human DNA. As a result, there is a basic harmony between the individual and the universe. Thus, the individual is a microcosm of the universe, which is a macrocosm. (Subba Rao, “Jyotish Unravels Mystery of Origin of Life”).

The same concept has been mentioned right from the Vedic period in our Indian Knowledge System. When the elements are in harmony, the vibration of the same element in the form of planets and stars, significantly has an effect within the human Body as well. This was the underlying science behind the Jyotisha which predicts with the placement and vibration of the planetary positions. Indian Astrology is a form of complete advanced space science which was taken to the practical application via prediction of planetary position.

Muthuswamy Dikshitar and Navagraha Kriti-s

Muthuswamy Dikshitar¹ was a prominent Carnatic music composer and one of the Trinity of Carnatic music, along with Tyagaraja and Syama Sastri. He is well known for his beautiful compositions, profound spirituality, and raga and tala mastery. Dikshitar is renowned for his Navagraha kritis, a set of 9 compositions that are among his most important contributions to Carnatic music. Each Navagraha kriti is a musical homage to a particular celestial body that evokes the attributes, meanings, and mythical significance of that entity. These works are profound spiritual expressions as well as musical classics, reflecting Dikshitar's great mastery of astrology and spiritual symbolism.

Objective of the Study

To critically analyse Dikshitar’s compositions on Navagraha, with special reference to ‘Suryamurthe’, to reveal the scientific and spiritual principles underlying Indian Astrology, shedding light on its integration with modern understanding while showcasing the depth of wisdom preserved in music.

¹ (1775-1835)

Research Methodology

Data from various online and offline sources were collected, which includes various articles and books relating to the chosen topic. Literatures such as Journal articles and books were reviewed on the basis of astrology and its underlying science. Qualitative analysis has been carried out on the lyrical part of Navagraha Kriti – Suryamurthe, of Muthuswamy Dikshitar. It was followed by the comparative analysis on lyrics of Suryamurthe kriti and the scientific aspects of Astrology that was imbibed in the lyrics. A critical analysis has been carried out relating the mythological content figuring in composition and the scientific principle attached.

ANALYSIS

To carry forward the analysis, the translation of the lyrics and its meaning were taken from the Book of Sri T.K. Govinda Rao - “Compositions of Mudduswami Dikshitar”, which served as a basic aid.

As mentioned earlier, for this particular study only the composition ‘Suryamurthe’ have been chosen and some special common concepts figuring in the Navagraha kriti-s were also was analysed.

Suryamurthe – Sourashtra Raga – Dhruva tala

Our Indian Mythology beautifully defines the 2 dimensions of an energy as Lord and his consort. The whole mythological stories were based on this principle of the energy dimensions. In the composition ‘Suryamurthe’, it was beautifully mentioned in the Pallavi as: सुन्दरछायाधिपते - *sundarachāyādhipate* – which refers Surya as lord of Chaya – the shadow. Light and shadow are the two dimensions of light.

Karma is the fundamental element for the life in the earth, as mentioned in Veda-s and also in the cosmic law of science. In the Anupallavi of the composition, it is mentions as: कार्यकारणात्मक जगत्प्रकाश - *kāryakāraṇātmaka jagatprakāśa* – which brilliantly refers Sun as the ultimate source of light for the earth which is driven by the cause-and-effect cycle.

The word कर्मसाक्षिणे - *karmasākṣiṇe* – figuring in the charanam of the composition was incorporated with reference to the similar verse in Rig Veda, where it is mentioned that Sun is the one common lord of mankind and the witness to everything. (Janaki)

In Indian mythology, Sun’s vehicle is portrayed as a chariot driven by 7 horses. This aspect of mythology was brilliantly incorporated in the charana of the composition as: दिव्यतर सप्ताश्वरथिने - *divyatara saptāśvarathine* – which represents the seven colours that are formed by the dispersion of Sun light.

Muthuswamy Dikshitar also mentions the mantra with which the lord Surya can be worshipped. Along with the mentioning of the mantra, he beautifully inserts the Raga mudra into the composition as: सौराष्टार्ण मन्त्रात्मने - *saurāṣṭārṇa mantrātmane* – which represents the eight syllabled mantra, which has its mention in the Suryatapinyupanishad as: अत्र सोरमनूनि प्रवक्ष्यामि निगमोदितानि । घृणिरिति द्वे अक्षरे । सूर्य इति त्रीणि । आदित्य इति त्रीणि । एतद्वे सावित्रस्याष्टाक्षरं पदं श्रियाभिषिक्तम्॥ - *atra soramanūni pravakṣyāmi nigamoditāni . gṛṇīrīti dve akṣare. sūrya iti trīṇi. āditya iti trīṇi. etadve sāvitrasyāṣṭākṣaram padam śriyābhiṣiktam.* – where the eight syllabled sloka is: ॐ घृणिः सूर्य आदित्य. It is also mentioned in the Upanishad that “On the constant recitation and meditation of the mantra, one can realise Aditya as light, bliss, immortality, the brahmana and all the three worlds”. (Janaki)

Rāśi Allotment or Allotment of Zodiac Sign

As per Indian Astrology, the Zodiac signs/ Rāśi is allotted to only 7 planets of Astrology, which eliminates Rahu and Ketu, as they were just two nodal positions of the moon – ascending and descending node. The seven planets are allotted with twelve zodiac signs as:

GRAHA	RĀŚI ALLOTTED
Surya	Simha
Chandra	Karka
Angaraka	Mēsha and Vrścika
Budha	Mithuna and Kanya
Brihaspati	Dhanus and Mīna
Sukra	Tula and Rishabha
Sani	Makara and Kumba

The zodiac sign was the result of the 12 division of each 30 degrees' keeping the earth as its centre point. Indian Astrology follows Geocentric model and not the actual structure of Solar System. Geocentric model is the scientific model used in Astronomy as well. (Subba Rao, “Sunlight in the Genesis of Principles of Jyotisha (a Vedanga)”)

In Indian Astrology the Sun and Moon are often grouped together as moon is a reflection of Sun’s light for earth. Thus, the total entities for the lordship becomes 6. Two signs each were allotted to all the six entities, where sun and moon together gets 2 signs and other planets gets 2 signs each. The assigning of lordship starts with the Leo – Simha Rāśi and starts with the Graha Sun. After the allotment of signs to Sun and the moon the signs are allotted to the planets in same order as shown in the Geocentric model. (Subba Rao, “Sunlight in the Genesis of Principles of Jyotisha (a Vedanga)”).

As mentioned earlier, the signs are formed with the division of the plane into 12, with 30 degrees' each. This resulted with the 12 constellations which are predominant in their section of 30 degrees'.

These constellations were given shape and names, which are followed till date in Indian Jyotisha.

Colours of Planets

The colours of all the nine graha-s are mentioned in precise in the compositions of Muthuswamy Dikshitar, which has its reference from Jyotisha/Indian Astrology. The colours mentioned by Dikshitar in his kriti-s and the relevance of the same in science are:

Graha	Colour mentioned by Dikshitar in composition	Colour given by Nasa
Surya – Sun	सौवर्ण स्वरूपात्मने (golden)	
Chandra – Moon	शरच्चन्द्रिकाधवलप्रकाशगात्रं (Shining White)	

Budha – Mercury	कुङ्कुमसमद्युतिं (saffron)	
Sukra – Venus	धवलगात्रम् (white)	
Angaraka – Mars	रक्ताङ्ग रक्ताम्बरादिधरं (Red)	
Brihaspati – Jupiter	निरञ्जनाय (tintless)	
Sani – Saturn	कालाञ्जनकान्तियुक्तदेहं (blackish grey)	

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

Muthuswamy Dikshitar has mastered the Indian Astrology i.e., Jyotisha and composed compositions by incorporating all the important concepts of Jyotisha. Jyotisha, a Vedanga, which was studied and practised by Indian right from ancient times, describes about the zodiac signs which are constellations, colour of planets, cosmic law and many more scientific principles, which were the very recent development in the field of science of present day. The Indian knowledge has been kept aside by the developing scientific world tagging it to be a pseudoscience.

The above analysis proves the mythological stories pertaining to Navagraha has an underlying advanced scientific aspect as well, and it is not just a myth. It also proves that, that Dikshitar's Navagraha kriti not only emphasizes the intricate relationship between astrology and music but also serves as a compelling case for the integration of traditional wisdom with contemporary scientific understanding.

RELEVANCE OF THE STUDY

This study opens avenues for interdisciplinary exploration, encouraging scholars to delve deeper into the intersections of music, astrology and astronomy to unravel the hidden gem of knowledge that have been preserved through ages.

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